

Reaction of Copper(II) Dithiocarbamates with Nitric Oxide

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Pure and dry nitric oxide gas was passed through chloroform solutions of N,N'-diethyl-, N-morpholyl- and N-piperidyl dithiocarbamates of divalent copper at 0°, and three new nitrosyl complexes of copper(II) having the formula, $[\text{Cu.L.NO.H}_2\text{O}]$ were isolated and characterised. They are paramagnetic and I.R. spectra reveal the presence of uni-negative nitrosyl group and co-ordinated water. The electronic spectra indicate that the complexes are pseudotetrahedral in solid state. A trans- μ -hyponitrite structure was suggested to these compounds.

DITHIOCARBAMATO compounds of some transition metals are known¹⁻⁵ to give stable metal complexes with nitric oxide. The NO group in the metal nitrosyl complexes may be cationic NO⁺, anionic NO⁻ or nearly neutral; depending on the nature of the valence state of the metal and on the ligands. Whilst cationic behaviour of nitrosyl group is well reported, the uni-negative nature of NO group is comparatively less known^{6,7}. The present investigation describes the preparation and characterisation of three nitrosyl complexes of divalent copper containing uni-negative NO groups.

Experimental

Preparation of bis(N,N'-diethyl/N-morpholyl/N-piperidyl dithiocarbamate) Cu(II)

The sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids were prepared as given in the literature⁸. An aqueous solution of cupric acetate was reacted with an aqueous solution of the sodium salt of dithiocarbamic acid in the ratio 1:4. The greyish brown precipitate formed was suction filtered, washed repeatedly with water until free from acetate, followed by absolute alcohol and then air dried.

Preparation of nitrosyl complexes

To a chloroform solution of bis(N,N'-diethyl dithiocarbamate) copper(II) saturated with nitrogen, pure and dry nitric oxide gas was passed for 45 min at ice cold temperature. The colour of the solution changed from dark brown to green and finally a blue precipitate separated out, which was suction filtered, washed with alcohol and then dried *in vacuo*.

The preparation of (N-morpholyl/N-piperidyl dithiocarbamate) nitrosyl copper(II) complexes was exactly similar to the diethyl dithiocarbamate complex. The complexes were quite stable and could be stored for more than one month without any decomposition. They had high melting points and poor solubility in almost all common organic solvents except dimethyl formamide.

Analyses

Copper was estimated gravimetrically as $\text{CuPy}_2(\text{SCN})_2$. Sulphur was oxidized⁹ to sulphate in carbon

tetrachloride medium by addition of bromine followed by conc. nitric acid and the resulting sulphate was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO_4 . Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method.

Physical measurements

Infra-red spectra in the range 5000-650 cm^{-1} were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra on Nujol mull as well as in solution were recorded using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on solid specimens using Gouy method. The molar conductances were measured for $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution using a Toshinival conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 and a dip type cell.

Results and Discussion

The formation of dithiocarbamate complexes of Mn(II), Fe(II) and Co(II) is often accompanied by redox reaction facilitating the oxidation to trivalent state¹⁰. But in case of copper, a series of stable dialkyl dithiocarbamates of Cu(II) have been reported by Chatt¹¹ *et al.* The chemical analysis and paramagnetic behaviour of dithiocarbamate complexes reported now confirm the divalent nature of copper in the compounds.

Interestingly, on reaction with nitric oxide gas, one of the dithiocarbamate ligands of the bis-dithiocarbamate complexes of copper(II) has been replaced by one nitric oxide group and one water molecule as revealed by analysis. The resulting nitrosyl complexes are found to be paramagnetic with one unpaired electron on the copper atom (see Table). The low values of molar conductance in dimethyl formamide show that they are non-electrolytes. Hence, it is reasonable to assume that one uninegative bidentate dithiocarbamate ligand is replaced by one uninegative monodentate nitrosyl group and one neutral monodentate water molecule, such that divalency of copper is maintained after reaction. Infra-red spectra were recorded to throw some light on the nature of the bonded NO group and to get evidence for the co-ordinated water molecule.

TABLE
ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, INFRA-RED AND ELECTRONIC
SPECTRAL DATA (CM⁻¹) OF CU(II) COMPLEXES.

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	%Cu	%S	%N	Λ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	$\nu(N=O)$	ν_{max}
			Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)				
1. [Cu(DDC)(NO)(H ₂ O)]	Light Blue	>300	23.9 (24.5)	24.3 (24.7)	11.1 (10.8)	9	2.10	1100 br	19445,12900
2. [Cu(MDC)(NO)(H ₂ O)]	Green	>300	22.7 (23.2)	23.0 (23.4)	9.9 (10.2)	13	2.04	1115 br	19445,12120
3. [Cu(PDC)(NO)(H ₂ O)]	Light Green	>300	22.9 (23.4)	23.1 (23.6)	10.1 (10.3)	16	1.98	1110 br	20410,12120

DDC—N,N'-diethyl dithiocarbamate, MDC—N-Morpholyldithiocarbamate, PDC—N-Piperidyl dithiocarbamate, br—broad.

Infra-red spectra

Usually, dithiocarbamates act as bidentate ligands. But an example of monodentate behaviour was reported in case of a ruthenium complex¹², where the infra-red spectrum showed additional bands at 970–980, 1060–1065, 1260–1265, 1410 and 1460–1470 cm⁻¹ regions. The spectra of the compounds reported now show only the bands attributable to a bidentate behaviour of dithiocarbamate group but do not show any additional band in the above regions confirming the bidentate nature of the ligand.

Although the nature of nitrosyl group in the complexes is still in controversy, from infra-red spectral evidence, it has been generally accepted¹³ that the cationic NO⁺ stretching frequency falls in the range between 1940–1575 cm⁻¹, whereas the anionic NO⁻ stretching frequency is observed in the range 1200–1040 cm⁻¹. The behaviour of nitric oxide as a neutral ligand in the complexes does not seem to have been studied¹⁴ in detail. In the spectra of the nitrosyl complexes under study, broad bands are noticed (not given in the table) at ~3350 cm⁻¹ and ~1660 cm⁻¹ regions which can be assigned to co-ordinated water molecules. Further, strong broad bands are observed at about 1100 cm⁻¹ (see table) which can be definitely assigned to uninegative nitrosyl (NO⁻) groups. This NO⁻ group is isoelectronic with oxygen molecule and is expected to be paramagnetic with two unpaired electrons. There is no evidence for any unusual magnetic property of the compounds and hence as previously suggested by Raynor⁷, we also conclude that these complexes are dimers involving trans- μ -hyponitrite structure.

The similarity between N–O stretching frequency in the complexes and in the hyponitrite anion (~1130 cm⁻¹) suggests that the metal is bonded to the nitrogen but not to oxygen. This dimerisation involving the presence of a bridging hyponitrite group is also consistent with poor solubility and high melting points of the compounds.

Electronic Spectra

From the study of a variety of salicylaldimine complexes of Cu(II), Sacconi *et al.*¹⁵ suggested that

the planar complexes give a broad envelope in the region 14,000–16,000 cm⁻¹ and the pseudo tetrahedral complexes give three bands in the region, 8,700–10,000, 12,800–13,800; 19,200–20,800 cm⁻¹, the last one probably being due to a charge transfer band. In the present investigation, two bands centering near 20,000 and 12,500 cm⁻¹ are noticed and the third one could not be detected due to limitations of the range of the instrument used. Hence, the complexes are expected to be pseudo tetrahedral, which is also in conformity with a large orbital contribution to the magnetic moment. The solutions of the complexes in dimethylformamide, however, show one broad band at ~12,500 cm⁻¹ indicating¹⁶ distorted octahedral environment of the metal atom arising out of the co-ordination of two solvent molecules.

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References

1. B. F. G. JOHNSON and K. H. OBAIDI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 1668.
2. R. L. CARLIN, F. CANZIANI and W. K. BRATTON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **267**, 898.
3. H. BUTTNER and R. D. FELTHAM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 971.
4. L. CAMBI and L. MALATESTA, *Rend. Inst. Lombardo Sci.*, 1938, **71**, 118.
5. L. MALATESTA, *Gazzetta*, 1940, **70**, 729, 734.
6. W. P. GRIFFITH, J. LEWIS and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3993.
7. J. B. RAYNOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 997 and references therein.
8. C. P. PRABHAKARAN and C. C. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 1257.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., London, 1961, p. 467.
10. E. GLEEN and R. SCHWAB, *Angew. Chem.*, 1950, **62**, 320.
11. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and L. M. VENANZI, *Acta Chem. fenn.*, 1956, **B20**, 75.

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12. A. DOMENICANO, A. VACIAGO, L. ZAMBONELLI, P. L. LOADER and L. M. VENANZI, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 476.
13. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infra-red Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ord. Compounds," John Willey & Sons, N. Y. 1963, p. 183.
14. A. JAHN, *Z. Anorg. u. allgem. Chem.*, 1959, **301**, 301; W. Hieber and A. Jahn, *Z. Naturforsch*, 1958, **13b**, 195.
15. L. SACCONI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.
16. E. J. DUFF, M. N. HUGHES and K. J. RUTT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 2354.